
The Influence of Procurement Planning, Supplier Selection Planning, Information Systems and Regulations on the Success Rate of Selecting Suppliers of Goods or Services: Case Study on the Implementation of the Selection of Goods and Services Providers at the Financial Services Authority

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the variables that influence the success rate of goods or services provider selection at the Financial Services Authority. The independent variables in this study are General Procurement Planning, Provider Selection Planning, Information Systems, and Regulations. While the dependent variable in this study is the success rate of goods/services provider selection. This study uses a Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis technique based on Partial Least Square (PLS) using the Smart PLS analysis tool on 150 (one hundred and fifty) respondents. The results of the study indicate that General Procurement Planning, Provider Selection Planning, Information Systems, and Regulations have a positive and significant effect on the Success of Goods/Services Provider Selection at the Financial Services Authority.

1. Introduction

The Financial Services Authority, hereinafter abbreviated as OJK, was established in 2011 in accordance with Law No. 21 of 2011. OJK has the authority and duty to regulate and supervise activities in the financial services sector in a centralized, free, and accountable manner, so that it is expected to be able to organize activities in the financial services sector in an orderly, non-discriminatory, open, accountable manner, and can realize a sustainable and orderly financial system, and can protect the interests of financial service users and the public.

To support operational, administrative, asset procurement, and other supporting activities, the OJK utilizes funds from the State Budget (APBN) and/or levies imposed on those involved in the financial services sector. Budget allocation and use are based on generally accepted standards in the financial services sector. Exceptions apply to general cost standards, procurement

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procedures, and payroll systems in accordance with laws and regulations related to the State Budget (APBN), government procurement of goods and services, and payroll systems.

Reasonable standards in the financial services sector include cost standards generally adopted by the financial services sector or similar regulators, both nationally and internationally. This measure is taken to ensure that the Financial Services Authority (OJK) can adapt to the demands and dynamics of the financial services sector, both domestically and internationally. Meanwhile, general cost standards refer to the general cost norms applicable to Ministries and Institutions, in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations related to the State Budget.

Funding for OJK activities is essentially self-sustaining, funded through levies on financial services operators. However, OJK funding from the State Budget (APBN) remains necessary to meet operational needs when independent funding from financial services operators is insufficient to cover all operational activities. In the initial stages of OJK's formation, from 2013 to 2014, the OJK relied on the APBN. Subsequently, from 2015 onward, the OJK has replaced its funding source with levies from financial services operators.

To meet operational needs in the form of goods/services, the OJK conducts procurement through selection through goods/services providers and self-management. Supplier selection is a method of procurement of goods/services where the work is carried out by the Provider to meet the OJK's needs. Providers are Business Actors, Registered Partners, or Registered Partners from Profiling who sell goods/services for the OJK. Self-management is a method of procurement of goods/services where the planning, implementation, and/or supervision of the work is carried out by the OJK, either with or without other parties.

Procurement of goods or services is carried out with the aim of obtaining goods or services that are appropriate, measurable, and of high quality, in accordance with the needs of the OJK, which is implemented with the principles of effectiveness, efficiency, good governance, openness and competition, and the application of risk management. Risk management in procurement of goods/services includes the application of risk analysis at each phase of the procurement process as a step to reduce the impact that may arise from potential risks.

In general, the procurement of goods or services at the OJK is carried out electronically using the SI-PROJEK application, with stages including general planning, selection of providers, implementation of agreements with providers, delivery and acceptance of work results, management of Registered Partners/Registered Partners Profiling Results, and the OJK Catalog. The implementation of provider selection using the Direct Purchase method and Provision of Plots and/or Buildings is excluded from the use of SI-PROJEK. In the event of technical disruptions or some or all of the modules in SI-PROJEK are not yet available, the procurement of goods or services is carried out manually for some or all stages of the procurement of goods or services.

Procurement of goods/services is a critical task supporting the continuity of OJK operations and must be properly mitigated to minimize potential operational risks. Successful supplier selection will significantly impact the continuity of OJK's day-to-day operations in carrying out its core duties and functions.

Procurement of goods or services at the OJK is generally conducted through a provider selection method for all types of procurement (goods, construction services, other services, and consulting services). Procurement of goods or services using providers involves business actors as parties who provide goods/services required by the OJK in accordance with procurement packages outlined in the General Plan List for Procurement of Goods or Services which is determined every January and updated throughout the current budget year.

Supplier selection methods are divided into several selection methods based on the Self-Estimated Price (HPS) for each procurement package and type. Supplier selection methods include direct selection, direct appointment, repeat orders, direct procurement, direct purchasing, catalog purchasing, contests, and tenders/selection.

Based on data on supplier selection that has been carried out using direct selection or direct selection, tender or selection, direct appointment, and repeat-order methods in 2019 to 2023, it is known that out of 2,425 procurement packages, there are 561 procurement packages that failed in the supplier selection process, while the remaining 1,854 did not experience failure. Based on this data, the percentage of failure to the total number of procurement packages is 23.13%. Of the 561 packages that experienced failure, 200 packages were cancelled and 361 packages were re-selected until a supplier was found to be determined as the winner. There are several factors causing the high rate of failure in the selection of goods/services providers, including: Poor general procurement planning, Inaccurate supplier selection planning, Information systems used that are not well integrated and Regulatory Systems that are not implemented properly. Thus, it can be concluded that the number of re-selections is still quite high and fluctuates every year.

The recapitulation data for the number of procurement packages and the number of procurement packages that failed in the supplier selection process is as shown in the following table:

Table 1. Recapitulation of the Number of Goods or Services Procurement Packages

Procurement Year	Number of Packages	Number of Packages That Failed	Failure Percentage
2019	215	77	35.81%
2020	664	188	28.31%
2021	664	134	20.18%
2022	561	98	17.47%
2023	321	64	19.94%
Total	2425	561	23.13%

Based on the data in Table 1, it can be concluded that there is a phenomenon in the procurement of goods/services at the OJK, namely a high failure rate in selecting suppliers, and this failure rate fluctuates. Given this phenomenon, researchers are interested in investigating the factors contributing to failure in supplier selection, so that these factors can be effectively mitigated to reduce the failure rate in the supplier selection process.

Research on this topic has been carried out by previous studies, including the following: ResearchThe analysis of factors that impact the quality of procurement of goods or services in the Gorontalo Provincial Government was carried out using a quantitative methodology with independent variables in the form of HPS (X1), procurement schedule (X2), honesty (X3), selection method (X4), and as a dependent variable, namely the quality of procurement implementation (Y).The findings in this journal state that the HPS variable has a negative and significant impact on the quality of procurement implementation by the Gorontalo Provincial Government. Meanwhile, the variables of procurement schedule, honesty, and selection method have a negative and significant impact on the quality of procurement implementation. The journal concludes that the technical skills of procurement officials need to be continuously improved through procurement training or certification. Furthermore, the procurement process must be carried out in accordance with applicable provisions for the procurement of goods or services. In this journal, the technical capabilities of procurement officials should also be a variable studied,

The Influence of Procurement Planning, Supplier Selection Planning, Information Systems and Regulations on the Success Rate of Selecting Suppliers of Goods or Services: Case Study on the Implementation of the Selection of Goods and Services Providers at the Financial Services Authority
(Nanang Ariyanto, Harjum Muharam)

so that it is possible to draw conclusions about whether the quality of the resulting procurement is supported by the quality of its human resources.(Ahmad et al., 2017).

Ade Frankoe, Kamaludin, and Fadli conducted research related to the impact of planning in the electronic budgeting and procurement process on the level of budget absorption.. This journal uses a quantitative method with independent variables in the form of Budget Plan (X1), Government Procurement of Goods or Services (X2), and APBD Size (X3) which is also a control variable. The dependent variable in this journal is Budget Realization (Y). The findings in this journal state that the three variables (Budget Plan, Government Procurement of Goods or Services and APBD Size) have a positive influence on Budget Realization, which means that the better the budget plan, the better the procurement of government goods or services, and the larger the APBD size, the better the budget realization will be.(Frankoe, 2021).

Sawidar, Muttaqin, and AnitaRauzana conducted research on factors in the implementation of electronic government procurement of goods or services that have an impact on the level of budget realization in the city of Sabang.This study uses a quantitative method with independent variables in the form of System Quality (X1), Openness (X2), Accountability (X3), Market Access and Business Competition (X4), Efficiency (X5), Monitoring and Audit (X6), and Access to Information (X7). The dependent variable used in this paper is Budget Realization (Y). The findings in this paper state that all variables have a positive effect on budget realization. Thus, if the procurement factors that are independent variables are improved, then budget realization will also increase.(Sawidar et al., 2018).

AriPrasetyo conducted research on the determining factors in the successful implementation of electronic procurement at Bappenas. This study used a quantitative method with independent variables consisting of systems and technology, organization and management, and practices and processes. The dependent variable was the success of electronic procurement implementation. The findings in this paper indicate that all variables have an influence on the successful implementation of electronic procurement.(Prasetyo, 2019).

HaryonodoResearch related to electronic procurement and the effectiveness of government procurement of goods/services in Singkawang, West Kalimantan, using quantitative methods with the independent variable being the implementation of electronic procurement and the dependent variable being the effectiveness of procurement staff performance, and the intervening variable being leadership support. The findings in this journal state that the variable of electronic procurement implementation has a significant influence on the effectiveness of procurement staff performance. Leadership support is proven to strengthen the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. This implies the need to unify perceptions between leaders and staff regarding the benefits of electronic procurement. This study has not looked at several other variables such as service quality, information quality, system quality, satisfaction of parties who use electronic procurement applications.(Haryono, 2022).

StudyrelatedThe determinants influencing the success of construction procurement in Surabaya were analyzed using quantitative methods with independent variables being Procurement Success, Security and Authentication, Technology Standards, Planning and Governance, Policy and Regulation, Reengineering Process, System Mix, User Acceptance, Provider Involvement, and Leadership, with the dependent variable being Construction Procurement Success for Public Infrastructure Projects in Surabaya City. The findings in this journal state that the most dominant determinants of procurement success are Security and Authentication, Technology Standards, Planning and Management, while the other six factors are considered to have no effect on procurement success. Research on operational risks in the

selection of goods/service providers has been conducted by previous researchers, however, no one has examined the success rate of goods/service provider selection with similarities in factors that influence the success rate comprehensively.(Safitri et al., 2020).

ConcerningwithBased on the background of the problem, the gap phenomenon, and the research gap that have been explained, the research was compiled with the title "The Influence of Procurement Planning, Supplier Selection Planning, Information Systems and Regulations on the Success Rate of Goods or Services Provider Selection (Case Study on the Implementation of Goods and Services Provider Selection at the Financial Services Authority)". This research aims to analyze the variables that influence the success rate of provider selection at the OJK, with the hope that operational risks can be mitigated properly, especially mitigating provider selection failures, so that the need for goods/services can be met according to target.

2. Methods

This research uses a quantitative approach, utilizing primary data obtained through direct observation by the researcher of the research subjects. The data for this study comes from primary data obtained through direct observation, question-and-answer sessions, and the distribution of questionnaires to informants.(Sugiyono, 2013).

The primary data from this study comes from a questionnaire from Google Form which was filled out online by respondents (OJK employees). The population is the total number of elements to be studied (Cooper and Schindler, 2014). The population in this study is the OJK officials/employees who have been appointed as Technical Teams, Commitment Making Officers, Selection Implementation Teams, or Work Control Teams for all procurement packages whose supplier selection is carried out by the Logistics Department. The sample represents a portion of the quantity or attributes found in the research population. When a population is too large for researchers to examine further, a research sample is essential. Limitations can result from limited resources, time, or capacity of the researchers. The research population used must be appropriately and accurately represented in the research sample (Sugiyono, 2019).

The number of samples used as data sources for the research will be determined using the Structural Equation Model analysis technique. Sampling was conducted using a purposive sampling technique, namely by taking a portion of the population that meets the requirements. Sample selection was carried out based on data that meets the requirements and is in accordance with the objectives and problems of the research. The sample criteria in this study were OJK officials/employees who had been appointed as Technical Team (Preparer Selection Plan), Commitment Making Officer, Selection Implementation Team, or Work Control Team for the procurement package that was the research sample.

Hair et al. (2010) stated that the sample size should be at least five to ten times the number of observations. The number of respondents is adjusted to the number of question indicators used in the questionnaire, assuming $n \times 5$ observed variables (indicators) to $n \times 10$ observed variables (indicators) (Hair in Sitompul, 2021). This study contained 26 questionnaire statements used to measure five variables, so the total sample size used in the study was $26 \times 5 = 150$ people.

In order to obtain the valid data needed for the research, data collection was conducted using field research methods using questionnaires. Questionnaires are a method that can be used to research a risk.(Melkianus Albin Tabun, Maria, Sushardi, Diyah Santi Hariyani, Murni Sulistyowati, Anwar, Banta Karollah, Mariana, Ria Indriani, Agustinus Moonti, Dwi Arini Nursansiwi, 2023)A questionnaire is a data collection method that involves the use of a questionnaire containing structured, written questions that are systematically arranged. Respondents are asked to complete the questionnaire based on their personal views related to the research problem. Afterward, a score is assigned for each answer. In addition, direct interviews with employees were conducted. The type of questionnaire used in this study is a

The Influence of Procurement Planning, Supplier Selection Planning, Information Systems and Regulations on the Success Rate of Selecting Suppliers of Goods or Services: Case Study on the Implementation of the Selection of Goods and Services Providers at the Financial Services Authority
(Nanang Ariyanto, Harjum Muharam)

closed-ended questionnaire, so respondents only choose from the provided answer alternatives. The questionnaire will be distributed to OJK employees.

3. Results and Discussion

Hypothesis Testing

Research hypothesis testing uses the t-statistic coefficient. The bootstrapping command outputs a t-statistic. Indicators with a t-statistic > 1.96 are considered significant (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). Indicators can also be considered influential if they have a p-value < 0.05 (Haryono, 2017).

Figure 1. Inner Model

The stages of testing the structural model (hypothesis testing) are carried out with the following steps:

Table 2. Hypothesis Testing

Variables	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
General Procurement Planning -> Successful Selection of Goods/Service Providers	0.247	0.248	0.068	3,630	0.000
Supplier Selection Planning -> Successful Selection of Goods/Service Suppliers	0.227	0.224	0.081	2,808	0.005

Variables	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Information System -> Success of Goods/Service Provider Selection	0.173	0.178	0.076	2,286	0.023
Regulation -> Successful Selection of Goods/Service Providers	0.362	0.360	0.080	4,509	0.000

Source: Test results using SmartPLS version 3.0, 2025

Based on Table 2, the results of the hypothesis testing can be concluded as follows:

- 1) Hypothesis H1 General Procurement Planning To Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers General Procurement Planning has a t-statistic value 3,630 > 1.96, p-value 0.000 < 0.05 and original sample 0.247 then H1 is accepted, meaning General Procurement Planning has a positive and significant impact on the success of selecting providers of goods/services..
- 2) Hypothesis H2 Supplier Selection Planning To Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers Supplier Selection Planning has a t-statistic value 2,808 > 1.96, p-value 0.005 < 0.05 and original sample 0.227 then H2 is accepted, meaning Supplier Selection Planning has a positive and significant influence on the success of selecting goods/service providers..
- 3) Hypothesis H3 Information Systems To Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers Information Systems has a t-statistic value 2,286 > 1.96, p-value 0.023 < 0.05 and original sample 0.173 then H3 is accepted, meaning Information Systems has a positive and significant influence on the success of selecting goods/service providers..
- 4) Hypothesis H4 Regulation To Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers Regulation has a t-statistic value 4,509 > 1.96, p-value 0.000 < 0.05 and original sample 0.362 then H4 is accepted, meaning Regulation has a positive and significant influence on the success of selecting goods/service providers.

4. Discussion

The Influence of General Procurement Planning on the Success of Goods/Service Provider Selection

Based on the calculation results, the t-statistic value obtained is 3,630 which means > 1.96 and a sig. value of 0.000 below 0.05, then H1 is accepted, which means that General Procurement Planning has a positive and significant influence on the Success of Selecting Goods/Service Providers, meaning if General Procurement Planning increases then there will be an increase in the level Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers and statistically has a significant effect. Based on the results of data processing with SmartPLS version 3.0, it is known that the path coefficient value General Procurement Planning to Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers as big as 0.247, which means that General Procurement Planning has a positive and significant effect on the Success of the Selection of Goods/Service Providers in the Implementation of the Selection of Goods and Service Providers at the Financial Services Authority.

Inappropriate planning can result in targets not being achieved and can even increase potential risks. (Arta et al., 2021). General procurement planning must be prepared by the Work Unit (Satker) based on the respective Work Plan and Budget (RKA) for all procurement packages worth more than fifty million rupiah. According to (Ahmad et al., 2017), procurement schedules have a positive and significant impact on the quality of procurement implementation. Therefore, it can be concluded that high procurement schedule efficiency will also result in high

The Influence of Procurement Planning, Supplier Selection Planning, Information Systems and Regulations on the Success Rate of Selecting Suppliers of Goods or Services: Case Study on the Implementation of the Selection of Goods and Services Providers at the Financial Services Authority
(Nanang Ariyanto, Harjum Muharam)

procurement quality. This is also in line with the research conclusions.(Messakh et al., 2013), where poor job performance is caused by delays in completing the work and increasing costs agreed in the contract.

The Influence of Supplier Selection Planning on the Success of Goods/Service Supplier Selection.

Based on the calculation results, the t-statistic value obtained is 2,808 which means > 1.96 and the sig. value of 0.005 is below 0.05, then H2 is accepted, which means that Supplier Selection Planning has a positive and significant influence on the Success of Goods/Services Provider Selection, meaning if Supplier Selection Planning increases then there will be an increase in the level Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers and statistically has a significant effect. Based on the results of data processing with SmartPLS version 3.0, it is known that the path coefficient value Supplier Selection Planning to Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers is as big as 0.223, which means that the Planning for the Selection of Providers has a positive and significant effect on the Success of the Selection of Goods/Service Providers in the Implementation of the Selection of Goods and Services Providers at the Financial Services Authority.

The supplier selection plan is prepared and determined by the Commitment Making Officer (PPK) in the form of a Supplier Selection Plan (RPP) document consisting of the Terms of Reference (KAK), Own Estimated Price (HPS), and Draft Contract. The RPP is required if the supplier selection method used is direct selection, direct appointment (other than for goods and services related to art or in urgent circumstances), direct procurement, catalog purchases, contests, and tenders. According to (Ahmad et al., 2017) The procurement schedule has a positive and significant impact on the quality of procurement implementation. Therefore, it can be interpreted that high procurement schedule efficiency will significantly impact procurement quality. This is also in line with research.(Messakh et al., 2013) which stated that poor job performance was caused by delays in completing the work and increasing costs agreed in the contract.

The Influence of Information Systems on the Success of Selecting Goods/Service Providers.

Based on the calculation results, the t-statistic value obtained is 2,286 which means > 1.96 and the sig. value of 0.023 is below 0.05, then H3 is accepted, which means that the Information System has a positive and significant influence on the Success of Selecting Goods/Service Providers, meaning if Information Systems increases then there will be an increase in the level Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers and statistically has a significant effect. Based on the results of data processing with SmartPLS version 3.0, it is known that the path coefficient value Information System to Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers is as big as 0.173, which means that the Information System has a positive and significant influence on the Success of the Selection of Goods/Service Providers in the Implementation of the Selection of Goods and Service Providers at the Financial Services Authority.

The implementation of supplier selection using the direct purchasing method and the provision of land and/or buildings is still done manually, while other selection methods such as direct selection, direct appointment, repeat orders, direct procurement, contests, and tenders must be done electronically through the SI-PROJEK application. SI-PROJEK is a procurement application developed by the OJK, similar to the E-Procurement application owned by the

Government Goods/Services Procurement Policy Agency (LKPP). According to (Septiawan, 2018) E-Procurement embodies transparency, efficiency, and effectiveness in the procurement process to increase public trust, especially among goods/services providers, so that they are interested in participating in the procurement process. With increasing interest from goods/services providers in participating in procurement, the success rate of provider selection will also increase. Findings in the journal (Aristamy & Hendrawati, 2020) shows that electronic procurement applications make it much easier for users in the procurement process for goods or services, because it is easier and minimizes the use of hard copies of procurement-related documents.

The Influence of Regulations on the Success of Selecting Goods/Service Providers.

Based on the calculation results, the t-statistic value obtained is 4.509 which means > 1.96 and sig. value 0.000 below 0.05 then H4 is accepted, which means that Regulation has a positive and significant influence on the Success of Goods/Service Provider Selection, meaning that if Regulation increases there will be an increase in the Success rate of Goods/Service Provider Selection and statistically has a significant influence. Based on the results of data processing with SmartPLS version 3.0, it is known that the coefficient value of the Regulation path on the Success of Goods/Service Provider Selection is 0.362, which means that Regulation has a positive and significant influence on the Success of Goods/Service Provider Selection in the Implementation of Goods and Services Provider Selection at the Financial Services Authority.

A better understanding of regulations and the increasing detail of regulations applicable to the procurement of goods/services are important keys to realizing Good Corporate Governance (GCG) in the implementation of procurement of goods/services. Research conducted by (Juliani & Sholihin, 2014) This indicates that knowledge of regulations is one of the factors influencing budget absorption for procurement of goods/services. The absorption of the budget for procurement of goods/services automatically indicates that the procurement process has been successfully implemented, with one of the factors being a good understanding of the regulations related to procurement of goods/services. (Love et al., 2008). Human resources' understanding of procurement regulations will influence the quality of procurement planning and packaging strategies, which will ultimately affect the success rate of supplier selection. Human resources' understanding of procurement regulations will also be influenced by the sheer number of regulations that must be studied and adhered to.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of research on 150 respondents, namely the OJK officials/employees who have been appointed as Technical Team (Preparers of Provider Selection Plans), Commitment Making Officers, Selection Implementation Team, or Work Control Team related to the influence of procurement planning, supplier selection planning, information systems and regulations on the success rate of selecting goods or service providers, then the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. General Procurement Planning has a positive and significant influence on the success of the selection of goods/service providers in the implementation of the selection of goods and services providers at the Financial Services Authority, meaning if General Procurement Planning increases then there will be an increase in the level Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers and statistically has a significant influence.
2. Supplier Selection Planning has a positive and significant influence on the success of the selection of goods/service providers in the implementation of the selection of goods and services providers at the Financial Services Authority, meaning if Supplier Selection

The Influence of Procurement Planning, Supplier Selection Planning, Information Systems and Regulations on the Success Rate of Selecting Suppliers of Goods or Services: Case Study on the Implementation of the Selection of Goods and Services Providers at the Financial Services Authority
(Nanang Ariyanto, Harjum Muharam)

Planning increases then there will be an increase in the level Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers and statistically has a significant influence.

3. Information Systems has a positive and significant influence on the success of the selection of goods/service providers in the implementation of the selection of goods and services providers at the Financial Services Authority, meaning if Information Systems increases then there will be an increase in the level Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers and statistically has a significant effect.
4. Regulation has a positive and significant influence on the success of the selection of goods/service providers in the implementation of the selection of goods and services providers at the Financial Services Authority, meaning if Regulation increases then there will be an increase in the level Success in Selecting Goods/Service Providers and statistically has a significant influence.

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